

Answer Sheet for Elementary Scientist Exam

Questions

By

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Subject: Physical Science and the Fundamental Knowledge of the Cosmos

Questions:

This Socratic taboo questionnaire provides an unambiguous answer to the question of whether you are certified as an elementary scientist. Only proven elementary scientists are potential reliable sources on elementary issues. The question of whether or not you are a basic scientist with a Ph.D. is irrelevant to an elementary probandum of this article. ‘Elementary’ means most fundamental in the superset cosmos.

1. Are you a homo sapiens? If not please state what you are. If you are a computer please shut down. If you are homo sapiens but don’t accept the Grand Goal of the decent survival of homo sapiens then please shut up and enlighten us on what your opinion is after you’ve died.

2. Do you accept the Grand Axiom as the exclusive elementary axiomatic assumption of One Consistent Cosmos? Consistent means absolutely loophole-free complete and absolutely no contradictions in the superset cosmos. If not, then no elementary scientific discourse is possible. So, please shut up, be attentive, and return when you do. For, if real magic exists then all the science and the scientific method are per logical definition falsified. An open mind has its limits given the Grand Goal.

3. Do you claim to have solved all the first three rising complexity levels of the elementary questions in science and do you provide all the geometry and other mathematical theorems on which all further non-pseudo infinite incomplete science can logically be based in One Law of Nature? If you don’t, please shut up, be attentive, and return when you do.

4. Do you claim to have the elementary and basic scientific instruction manual of the instrument brain and that of the collective instrument brain as the physics of psychology based on the One Law of Human Nature that is consistent with the One Law of Nature and can you prove to have best practice applied it successfully in all of several fields? If not, please shut up, be attentive, and return when you do.

5. Have you studied at least both of my DOI publications?

ONE LAW OF NATURE MAKES ONE LAW OF HUMAN NATURE <https://zenodo.org/records/10727529>

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THE UNAMBIGUOUS 1000 ELEMENTARY TERMS, DEFINITIONS, AND DESCRIPTIONS IN ELEMENTARY SCIENCE, COURTROOMS, AND SCHOOLS <https://zenodo.org/records/10254851>

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If not, please shut up, be attentive, and come back when you very precisely and respectfully can show any data that is incorrect or not dealt with that you or others have consistently dealt with. If any such major error amounting to valid falsification exists it should be very easy to be shown. This is logical because the claim in this model is that it's all classical mechanics. When anyone shows minor errors or omissions * that no doubt always will exist * these are irrelevant when corrected after giving a reasonable time to do so. This is because nitpicking is a fallacy. That science will always be incomplete is not inconsistent with having all elementary science as the simple rules and first three bases of the unfathomably complex game of the tree like the Tower of Science and Life. Basic 'if it works it works, don't ask why science' is a reality of basic science yet falsified as elementary science that requires proven know-why workability. The latter is proven by showing to have followed the prescribed procedure and by giving access to all the raw data containing the statistics proving the claimed best practice track record. The raw data is on my blog and site linked in the articles. Current Science is based on a falsified implicit claim of best practices because by theorem proven unsolvable and disgracefully demands absolute proof which they acknowledge to be impossible.

<https://risadvies.nl/elementary-scientist-exam-method/>

(Question Part has been collected from Gerhard Ris)

Answer to the Questions of the Elementary Scientist Exam:

Observation is the fundamental process through which humans perceive, analyze, and interpret the world around them. It involves using the senses to gather information and understand phenomena, events, or behaviors. Observation is not merely passive; it requires attention, intentionality, and often, interpretation. Whether in scientific research, everyday life, or artistic expression, observation plays a crucial role in acquiring knowledge, fostering understanding, and driving innovation. At its core, observation relies on the five senses: sight, hearing, touch, taste, and smell. These sensory inputs enable individuals to gather information about their environment and the objects within it. Through sight, for example, one can perceive shapes, colors, and movements, while hearing allows the detection of sounds and their variations. Touch provides information about texture, temperature, and pressure, while taste and smell discern flavors and odors. Together, these senses create a rich tapestry of perception, enabling individuals to experience and navigate the world. However, observation goes beyond mere sensory input; it involves cognitive processes that organize and make sense of the incoming information. Selective attention filters out irrelevant stimuli, allowing individuals to focus on specific aspects of their environment. This process is influenced by factors such as prior knowledge, expectations, and personal interests. For instance, a biologist observing a forest may pay particular attention to plant species relevant to their research, while a nature enthusiast might notice the intricate patterns of sunlight

filtering through the trees. Interpretation is another key aspect of observation. It involves assigning meaning to the observed phenomena based on individual perspectives, cultural backgrounds, and contextual factors. Two people may witness the same event but interpret it differently based on their prior experiences and beliefs. For example, a crowded marketplace may be perceived as vibrant and bustling by one person, while another may find it overwhelming and chaotic. Observation is integral to the scientific method, where it serves as the foundation for empirical inquiry and hypothesis testing. Scientists carefully observe natural phenomena, conduct experiments, and analyze data to uncover patterns, relationships, and underlying principles. Through systematic observation, researchers can formulate theories and models that explain complex phenomena, leading to advancements in knowledge and technology. In addition to its scientific applications, observation plays a crucial role in various fields, including education, healthcare, and the arts. Educators use observation to assess student learning, identify areas for improvement, and tailor instructional strategies to individual needs. Healthcare professionals rely on observation to diagnose illnesses, monitor patient progress, and provide personalized care. Artists use observation to capture the essence of their subjects, whether it be the play of light on a landscape or the subtle emotions of a portrait sitter. Observation is not without its limitations and biases. Human perception can be subjective and prone to errors, influenced by factors such as attentional biases, cultural norms, and cognitive shortcuts. Additionally, observations may be affected by the presence of the observer, altering the behavior of those being observed in what is known as the observer effect. Despite these challenges, observation remains a powerful tool for understanding the world and generating new knowledge. By honing their observational skills and approaching phenomena with curiosity and open-mindedness, individuals can unlock new insights, challenge assumptions, and contribute to the collective pool of human understanding. In conclusion, observation is a multifaceted process that involves the use of the senses, cognitive processes, and interpretation to gather information about the world. It is essential for scientific inquiry, everyday perception, and creative expression, enabling individuals to acquire knowledge, make sense of their experiences, and innovate in various fields. While subject to limitations and biases, observation remains a cornerstone of human cognition and a driving force behind progress and discovery.

However, we have discussed observation before answering the questions of the elementary scientist exam. So to say, observation is very important for an observer. Evidently, there are only two kinds of observers. Such as - relative observer and absolute observer.

Relative observer: A relative observer is one who observes and doesn't observe simultaneously. For him, most of the part of the universe always stays unobserved. A relative observer has two types of observation which are known as subjective observation and objective observation.

On the contrary,

Absolute observer: An absolute observer is one whose subjective observation and objective observation are equal. He is capable of observing from all perspectives simultaneously. That means, he is capable of perceiving and observing the extreme state of the universe. There is nothing new to discover for him. In a word, an absolute observer can't be regarded as a scientist and researcher.

Since generally humans and other animals aren't capable of perceiving and observing the ultimate, extreme state of the universe. Therefore, all humans including animals are relative observers. Mostly it is the humans who try to find out the mysterious and unknown term of the universe, it is the humans who collect data with observation because they don't know, it is the humans who become scientists and researchers. Hence, all animals and humans are relative observers. So what's the specialty in humans? The specialty in humans is that they have a well-structured body and intelligence. We humans are intelligent, and we have consciousness. A relative observer's observation is greatly linked to consciousness. So, I am a relative observer, and it is being the most fundamental identity than other identities. To know the universe, we have to gain knowledge through

observation. So, what's my opinion after my death? It is noteworthy that if I stay alive, my opinion won't be changed until I change, and I have never experienced death before. Therefore, I don't know how I will feel after death. Will it feel like the same as alive just I won't be able to interact with the universe and be bodiless, or I will have a dreamless sleep? It is very uncertain according to scientific explanation (Feature of a relative observer). Even there can be more things that we have never thought. There is no need to go there. We could simply ask, "How was our feeling before our birth?" The answer is also uncertain. I didn't feel any existence of me. I don't know what was my opinion, and I don't have data. I don't know either it was like I was moving without a body and leading a life or a dreamless sleep which is equivalent to not feeling the existence. But How did I confirm that I had a dreamless sleep, even dreamless sleep can be possible while staying alive. The fact is that none can gain consciousness by himself, and no can be unconscious by himself. What we normally call that as losing consciousness is nothing but losing awareness. It always happens, and we are very familiar with it. There is no tool to measure consciousness. Normally this universe may seem mindless, but from Oliver Denis, "Universe is a Turing machine." Actually, this universe expresses so many things but we can't detect because of not being observant. Here, an observant being gaining data through observation. However, no matter whatever the consciousness. It is one of the fundamental and essential terms of the universe. Let us go back to the point, how do I know about the feeling before my birth? All my knowledge has been gained from observation. Observation doesn't only include watching; it also indicates the way of gaining knowledge/data/information. While staying alive, we have passed a huge amount of time, but without some specific events, we forget about our activities on other days. However, our brain contains a sketch of those events. Whenever we see a picture, video... etc., we instantly remember. Even there are also those days which we have passed but we don't have in our memory. If someone who knows about that and tells me about the day, I will believe because I trust the person and I know the person. But imagine, a stranger tells you about that, if you have it in memory, you will be amazed how did he know. Otherwise, you will tell him, "You are lying. I don't feel any existence of me what you have mentioned. There is no such a day." It is a very important point that:

"Data/information with evidence helps us to perceive the existence of the past."

But obviously, we have to keep a sketch in our memory for verifying for finding similarities. Before our birth, if we had a life or we were separated from the body or we were having a dreamless sleep or not having existence are the same if we don't have data. It is not possible to confirm if we don't have a sketch in our brain of such days. Therefore, leading a life before birth and not having existence seem similar because we don't have data to verify. There is basically no way to confirm that we had existence before birth or not. Without data, leading a life will still feel as you had no existence and you don't know. We haven't counted it from death because all alive people never experienced death, but we have already experienced life from birth to now. Therefore, there was also time before our birth. So we have counted before our birth. Even we dream huge but most of them are forgotten. So we can't even feel the existence of those dreams once we had it. Above everything, we got a fundamental feature of humans, and it is known as a relative observer. This identity is more fundamental than Homo sapiens and animals. Even a memory lost person can be the best example. He feels no existence of him in the past. According to traditional quantum mechanics, an observer is a very fundamental term of science. Our observation can affect the reality, though it is totally negligible on the bigger scale. Furthermore, Albert Einstein had a great debate with Niels Bohr. Niels Bohr had mentioned, "Nature is very complex. Everything is random." On the contrary, Einstein said, "I want to think that the moon will stay at its own place if I don't observe." Moreover, he said, "God doesn't play dice." According to my point of view, both of them are correct. Again, I would like to add something to make it complete and that is: "God doesn't play dice but his not playing dice has turned into the effect of randomness and uncertainty for humans. It is for the fundamental feature of humans. That is God as an observer and humans as an observer aren't the same. Rather, humans are relative observers. There is nothing new to know for God, he knows everything from the backward and the forward. Everything is certain." Sorry for the confusion, let us come back to the point again. It was just an abstract expression. Here, we aren't discussing religion. However, basically on the classical scale those all weird phenomena of quantum mechanics are negligible. Our observation has no effect of it but at the quantum scale

those aren't negligible. Relativity is everywhere. Even in our observation too. That's the reason why we can't know quantum mechanics correctly with certainty and without probabilistic measurement. While using objective observation, we only measure with probability since we aren't certain. So, nature is probabilistic? Actually no. If nature remains certain, still we can't perceive that because we are relative observers and our subjective observation and objective observation aren't the same. According to our viewpoint, it will still behave probabilistically (at quantum scale), with effects also dependent on scale. Not everywhere. Moreover, there is a misunderstanding among some philosophers; they think that they are God and creator of the universe. They create something by observing. It is not valid. Again, we are reminded by Oliver Denis, "The universe is a Turing machine." It reminds us that even the universe has a mind and consciousness. What if nature is showing us what we call that we are creating? It is not impossible at all. On the other hand, a creator must have control of the total universe. But they don't have it. Most of the time, including us, they become the victim of the decision of nature. Moreover, being an absolute observer is a feature of a Creator. Hence, an absolute observer can't be a seeker, philosopher, or scientist. There is no need for it. A philosopher always wants to see the extreme state of the universe, whether an absolute observer never wishes to do so. It is not our aim to find where the absolute observer resides, who he is, and where is the evidence. Normally, this will lead to a religious debate. But here we have used it as an example to show the evidence that humans are not absolute but relative observers. Now, we will reveal another important feature about the relative observer, and that is:

"The more a relative observer will become observant, the more he will find mysterious phenomena in nature."

This is very important; as time passes, the more we are developing our technology and upgrading for detection, the more new things we are discovering (It has been indicated as being observant). Therefore,

"A relative observer should keep himself observant and he should contain an open-mind since his observation is relative, and he knows almost nothing about the universe."

For an example - Let us consider the period between 1600 to 2024. Just think about the evolution of physics. The more we have upgraded the tech, the more we have discovered new things. Those records in the journals are the evidence and those all research papers and this term "New discovery" are the evidence that human being a relative observer. It can be said that, "Evidence is the weak point of fact." Although fact is factual, but observer needs evidence to confirm because he is a relative observer. Even the term "For want of evidence" is the evidence of being a relative observer for human. We have noticed that you have emphasized the classical mechanics and have regarded that the current scientific community is going on the wrong way. However, if we consider the traditional quantum mechanics is wrong, still the classical mechanics to cosmology the subject of relative observer remains valid remains and undisputed. Therefore, yes. Magic exists when we don't know nothing about science. Real magic doesn't exist when we learn the scientific explanation of the phenomenon. Apparently those all miracles things have explanation but a relative observer needs to be observant to seek the explanation since he doesn't know. The universe contains so many things which is greater than what we know. It will always stay as greater. Even it will stay as greater for known things because we only see and understand them from our perspective. There is no context of higher dimensions. But if they exist, still there is no other way to find out unless the observer becoming more observant and he needs to be observant because he is relative observer, he can't claim to see and perceive the extreme state of the universe. Hence, as a relative observer I don't provide the extreme mathematical framework of nature. In a word, it is not possible to develop an extreme fixed mathematical framework of the universe which will describe everything from the micro to macro. Yes, I have checked the Doi. I am not regarding the string can't be found ..etc and the concept of one law is not applicable for everything. But we have to clear the everything. What is actually "Everything."? It is basically with belongs range what we have found until now. For now, the amount of much knowledge we have and phenomena we see in nature can be explained with a single law. But universe always contains more than

what we have. The main problem is that the more a relative observer will become observant over time, the more the observer will find new phenomenon in nature which will always challenge our developed model and we have to change the model. When once again, the relative observer will become more observant, he will find again more interesting unexplained phenomenon in the nature. It will stay like this....

“A relative observer’s observation type is naturally formed. It is proved. If we ask why and how it has formed. Currently we don't know and again we have proved that we are relative observers for not knowing.”

Since finding or having an extreme and ultimate, unchangeable model of nature based on one law, is just an approximation which will not be completed totally, So, it is not possible for a relative observer to see or perceive the extreme state of nature. To sum up, our universe is not only random but also complex, certain, easy..etc but it's depending on observer’s position and scale and also the type of observation. In a word, we need a pure and complete version of the “Theory of Observation (TO).”

[NB: The answers have been provided throughout the passage]

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Keywords: *Relativity; Observation; String; Law; Data; Information; Elementary; Exam; TO (Theory of Observation).*

Acknowledgements

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